

Marie Kaess Admitted to Cook County Medical Examiner's Office

On April 20 2023, Brian Paul Kaess received an email from the Cook County Medical Examiner's Office that read as follows:

"Good Afternoon

First and foremost, our condolences on the loss of your loved one. Your mother is registered as Marie Kaess in our records. Ms. Marie Kaess (DOB 12/4/45) came into our care under storage case number 069 OCT 12. Her cause of death was deemed to be Natural. The immediate cause is ruled as Acute Myocardial Infarction. Her physician signed the death certificate. Copies of Death certificates can be obtained through the Cook County Clerk's Office. They have a website: www.cookcountyclerk.com

If you have any additional questions feel free to call our main line at 312-666-0500.

Sincerely,

Medical Examiner's Office

2121 W Harrison St

Chicago, Il 60612"